

Educational Resource Management ... (Ebirim & Amadi, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045593>

Educational Resource Management for Sustainable Economic Development at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This paper focused on the qualitative study on educational resource management for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria: a systematic review. The paper discussed the meaning of educational resources management and its relevance at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Further, the paper delved into the major activities of resources management at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. This paper argued that educational resources management creates a sense of direction in resources management actions, reduces resources wastage and enhances effective instructional delivery with effective academic research without much delay and conflicts. This paper however maintained that resource planning and budgeting; resource provision and allocation; resource utilization and maintenance; resource improvement and supervision constitute the major activities of resources management at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. The paper therefore concluded that educational resources management must focus on adequate provision, proper allocation, efficient utilization, effective maintenance and regular improvement of all the available resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Resources Management; Educational Institutions; Sustainable Economic Development

Introduction

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Certainly, no developing economy promotes specific objectives and achieves any meaningful national goals in the absence of education. Education makes individuals ready for meaningful living in any economy and enhances sustainable development of such economy. Ebong (2006) believed that education provides opportunities for individuals to acquire knowledge, skills and attributes that shape and form the individuals for economic growth and national development. Additionally, Abraham (2020) submitted that education allows individuals and nations to discover opportunities and new ways to create job and create wealth. Unarguably, educational goals cannot be achieved without effective involvement and viable activities of educational resources management in educational institutions. Educational institutions are specialized form of organizations or establishments accredited to provide formal and non-formal education at different levels such as pre-primary, basic, primary, secondary and tertiary education levels among others. Educational institutions need resources to carry out activities and programmes of education in a bid to accomplish specific objectives.

Consequently, Ohia (2008) confirmed that educational institutions require resources in the form of quality teaching and non-teaching staff to carry out educational projects and activities. Resources serve as essential mechanism through which individuals' wants are satisfied and economy's goals actualized. Nyandema (2015) saw resources as the efficient and effective deployment of human skills, inventory and finance to support an institution when needed.

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Resources are vital ingredients of goals achievements hence; their management should not be taken for granted. Resource management involves adequate provision and proper allocation of required resources, their efficient utilization with effective maintenance and regular improvement for maximal achievement of goals. Educational resources are very important instrument of an economy goal's achievement. Educational resources are sources through which individuals have open access to education (Akpomi & Nwamadi, 2020). As further reasoned by Ogamba (2021), educational resources are assets available and anticipated for school operations in the economy. They are inputs that boost the activities and programmes of educational institutions to a great extent.

At tertiary level of education in Nigeria, educational resources exist in different forms and categories that can be classified into tangible and intangible assets. The tangible assets are visible inputs quantified into human, land, equipment, infrastructural facilities, instructional materials and capital. This form of assets can be seen, touch and transformed while the intangible assets are the invisible inputs that exist in the form of time availability, human knowledge, skills, abilities and competences among other human qualities. These assets can mostly be measured by the quality and quantity of outcome they produce. Intangible assets are invisible and indispensable due to the fact that the tangible assets cannot be utilized without the complement of intangible assets. Notably, Olelewe et al. (2014) identified funds dispensed and utilized, PTA levies, donations and internally generated revenue as educational resources. Similarly, Akpomi and Nwamadi (2020) added classrooms, lecture theatres, administrative block, laboratories, auditoriums, workshops, assembly halls, students' hostels, students' cafeteria and staff quarters.

In the revelations of Ebirim et al. (2023a), constant electricity power supply, well equipped ICT centers, adequate and functional computers, free and accessible internet services are among educational resources. Agabi (2010) highlighted more educational resources to comprise students and staff personnel, laboratory attendants, bursar, clerks, messengers, mail runners, gatekeepers, librarian, internet connectivity, school administrators and school planners. Similarly, Akpomi and Ordu (2009) identified textbooks, audio-visual and electronic instructional materials such as computers, tape recorder, video tape recorder, recorder, projector and other consumables like paper supply and writing materials as educational resources. Meanwhile, it could be understood that educational resources are divided into four major components which consist of human resources, material resources, time resource and financial resources. These resources are very important in educational institutions as none of them can function better in isolation of the other while trying to accomplish objectives of educational institutions particularly and the general goals of education in a developing economy such as Nigeria.

Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

Development means the improvement of peoples' lifestyle through improved education, improved incomes, skill acquisition and employment (Ebirim & Uzoukwu, 2023). Enwere and Ugwu (2013) maintained that sustainable development is a pattern of economic growth in which resources' use aims to meet human needs while preserving the environment so that these needs can be met not only in the present but for generations to come. Mbaji and Ebirim (2013) promote sustainable development as collective improvement and justifiable circulation of resources in all sections of an economy to improve the living standard of the masses both in the present and in the future. Sustainable economic development refers to the ability of different nations to get better on their economy with a view to increasing their productive capacities for the satisfaction of essential needs of their individuals in the economy (Ilume & Ebirim, 2016). Sustainable economic development carries connotation of lifelong economic transformation. It involves the emancipation of various units and departments of different levels of educational institutions from obstructions that affect their ability to develop and sustain their economy. Sustainable economic development involves minimizing resources wastage and creating opportunities for resources' optimization in the educational system to trigger economic growth. Sustainable economic development involves all round progress that

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takes place in all sections of a nation's economy that meets the educational needs of both present and future individuals.

Educational Resources Management at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Educational resources management describes those activities relating to the provision, allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the required resources available in educational institutions for attainment of specific objectives and general goals of education. Resources are those necessary inputs which institutions depend on for their survival and improvement (Obi & Ogbuagu, 2020). The required educational resources available in educational institutions need to be effectively and efficiently managed for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Management is a human action that facilitates the production of educational goods and services in educational institutions through the process of planning, organizing, coordination, controlling and evaluation of the available scarce resources required for enhanced quality educational delivery and for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Educational resources management is a task of educational management designed to achieve the purpose for which educational resources are made available in educational institutions. Asodike and Jaja (2014) declared that educational resources management is the organization of the resources existing in education sector with the aim of producing eminent graduates in the system. This declaration goes down to describe educational resources management as a crucial exercise that allows for quality assurance in educational institutions for achievement of educational goals. Mbaji et al. (2013) explained quality assurance as the establishment of standards in various educational processes and activities that lead to the attainment of quality results. Educational resources management is the activity that contributes to the design, assessment, monitoring and effective manipulation of the required resources available in tertiary educational institutions for sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Educational resources management is a collective activity of all those involved in the management of educational institutions aimed at improving quality of educational processes and programmes through the provision and allocation of resources, utilization and maintenance of resources, improvement and supervision of resources as well as evaluation and control of resources available in educational institutions. These resources are in terms of staff and students' personnel, infrastructural facilities, instructional materials, availability of limited time and finances at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Ihekwoaba and Maduiké (2016) added that educational resources management is the management of all relevant human and non-human resources that play various roles in promoting educational activities in educational system. It is the process of managing all human, material, non-material, audio-visual school environment and community materials available in an academic environment to facilitate academic activities and programme (Ebirim et al. 2023).

Relevance of Educational Resources Management at Tertiary Level of Education for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

Resources are very important element of goals' achievement. In order words, educational resources are most necessary in the attainment of sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. To achieve sustainable economic development in Nigeria, there is great need for effective management of scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria. Management is a process that concerned with the formulation of strategies, plan, policies and programmes with a view of achieving set organizational goals (Jack & Nzokurum, 2020). For that reason, educational resources management guides the planners, managers and administrators of educational institutions to formulate policies on resource provision and allocation based on educational goals to be achieved. Also, it guides them to strategize on the best approach to equitably distribute the

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available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development based on priority needs of various units and departments in different tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.

Undoubtedly, educational resources management is a collective activity targeted at tackling educational problems within educational institutions to create conducive work environment for teaching and non-teaching staff as well as students and other people who have direct contact with other activities and programmes within educational institutions. In the light of the above, educational resources management tries to utilize the potentials and efforts of all individuals in tertiary educational institutions by seeking cooperative participation of all the individuals involved in the process of mobilizing and utilizing the available scarce resources required to enhance quality educational delivery and sustain economic development in Nigeria. Further, Akpan and Etor (2015) argued that when resources are properly allocated, maintained and efficiently utilized in educational institutions, they are most likely to be of good quality in terms of the output. This goes down to indicate that educational resources management creates room for enhanced quality educational delivery at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Educational resources management involves making proper decisions on how best to utilize and maintain available scarce resources in educational institutions for the achievement of educational goals in any economy such as Nigeria. Decision making entails taking effective actions on matters concerning resources' allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement among other activities in educational institutions. Thus, educational resources management enables managers and administrators of educational institutions to determine priorities for actions in the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of required scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions for sustainable economic development in Nigeria. Abraham and Igwe (2006) noted that the actions of an administrator are guided by goals to be achieved and such requires that the administrator must be able to make good decision. Hence, educational resources management creates a sense of direction in the actions of managers and administrators in educational institutions towards decision making on proper allocation, efficient utilization, effective maintenance and regular improvement of all the required resources available in tertiary educational institutions for improved productivity and sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Indisputably, educational resources management exists for the purpose of resources wastage reduction in educational institutions and to provide opportunities for efficiency as well as improved productivity in any economy. With effective educational resources management practices, educational managers and administrators are able to minimize the possibility of resources wastage in tertiary educational institutions. Ebirim and Ali (2021) noted that many resources are expended in the course of producing educational commodities and when a significant reduction in the level of wastage of resources in educational system is achieved, it indicates increase in productivity. So, educational resources management creates opportunities for reduction in the level of wastage at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. It guides the educational managers and administrators to prepare institutional budgets according to needs and activities of various units and departments at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Equally, it prepares their mind to ensure that the institutional budgets are effectively communicated to guarantee proper compliance with the daily implementation policy and objectives of tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.

Most importantly, educational resources management enhances effective instructional delivery and effective academic research in educational institutions. Akpan and Etor (2015) were of the view that educational resources management involves the acquisition, utilization and administration of resources in higher education to enhance quality service delivery. On the other hand, Ogbodo (2011) posited that educational resources management creates avenue for judicious utilization and maintenance of human, materials, finance and other available scarce resources for the optimal achievement of set educational goals. In other words, educational resources management guides educational managers and administrators at tertiary level of education in Nigeria to strategize on the best approach

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to regularly evaluate and take inventory of instructional facilities and materials available in tertiary educational institutions for effective instruction and sustainable economic development in Nigeria. Through educational resources management, staff and students' activities are supervised regularly to determine in time areas of weakness that require immediate attention at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Once more, areas of job lapses in staff are being identified and corrected to enhance quality service delivery and to sustain economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Major Activities of Educational Resources Management at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Educational resources management covers a broad scope of activities. It involves making rational choice on proper allocation and efficient utilization of the required scarce resources available in educational institutions for the purpose of achieving educational goals and sustainable economic development in any economy of the world. The practice of educational resources management involves effective actions that must be initiated from rational decision making. Abraham and Igwe (2006) expressed that effective actions in organizations like tertiary educational institutions are predicated on correct decision making. The activities of educational resources management are guided by goals to be achieved. Goals are values determined to be achieved through the instrumentality of policies following appropriate strategies (Iwuchukwu, 2006). The more specific educational goals are the more major activities of educational resources management are directed towards the attainment of those goals and sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Educational resources management involves taking rational decision in a most efficient manner on the strategies for planning, budgeting, providing, allocating, utilizing, maintaining, improving, supervising, evaluating and controlling the available scarce resources required to enhance quality service delivery in educational institutions and to achieve the general goals of education. Taking rational decision in educational resources management involves making sound judgment on the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions for the attainment of sustainable economic development. On the whole, educational resources management exists for the outright reason of mobilizing, utilizing and maintaining the available scarce educational resources required for sustainable economic development through adequate planning, proper organizing and effective coordination of both human and non human resources in tertiary educational institutions. Anorue and Uchegbu (2021) confirmed that educational resources management leads to planning, organizing, coordinating, staffing, reporting, directing and evaluating human and material resources for the realization of set educational objectives.

The major activities of educational resources management are resource planning, resource provision, resource utilization, resource maintenance, resource improvement, resource supervision and control (Ebirim et al. 2023a). From the forgoing idea, the major activities of educational resources management can be declared to include; resource planning and budgeting, resource provision and allocation, resource utilization and maintenance as well as resource improvement and supervision. These activities according to Obi (2003) are basic in the management process of educational institutions. Through these resources management processes, managers and administrators of educational institutions are able to create sense of direction in resource management actions, reduce resources wastage, enhance effective instructional delivery and effective academic research as well as achieve educational goals without much delay and conflicts.

Resource Planning and Budgeting at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource planning and budgeting involve the process of identifying, forecasting and allocating various components of educational resources in terms of human, materials, finance and time to programmes and events at the right time. These activities ensure that educational programmes and activities at tertiary level of education are carried out on

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time based on budgets made. It involves assigning the right tasks to the right personnel and the right facilities and materials to the right programmes and activities at the right time (www.saviom.com). They also center on the allocation of tasks to resources in a way that optimize the efficiency of resources' use in tertiary educational institutions to improve productivity. Resource planning and budgeting activities guide educational managers and administrators in making rational decision on resource provision and allocation at tertiary level of education.

Resource Provision and Allocation at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource provision and allocation involve the process of making required resources available for use in educational institutions to accomplish specified goals at tertiary level of education. Resource provision and allocation centre on availability of human resources to perform services function and availability of instructional facilities and materials for quality instructional delivery. Resource provision and allocation aim at finding a balance between maximizing the productivity of available resources in tertiary educational institutions while avoiding over utilization of resources. Ogbonnaya (2005) opined that resource provision includes providing funds for greater profitability of educational institutions. This means that tertiary educational institutions welcome marginal funding to provide additional specialist support or facilities for students within the identified tertiary level of education. Additionally, resource provision and allocation centre on providing instructional materials and facilities for carrying out instructional activities at tertiary level of education.

Resource Utilization and Maintenance at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource utilization and maintenance are among the major activities of educational resources management which centre on efficient usage and proper care giving to all available resources for goals' attainment. Resource utilization and maintenance measure how resources are efficiently utilized and the extent to which proper care is given to resources against their availability (<https://www.eresourcescheduler.com>). Resource utilization and maintenance allow educational managers and administrators to identify resource problems at tertiary level of education in Nigeria, timely. They ensure specific educational resources are not over utilized and, or underutilized. They express that resources required for educational activities and programmes are utilized in conformity with identified policies and objectives of educational institutions to be accomplished at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Resource utilization and maintenance describe how managers and administrators of tertiary educational institutions plan educational programmes and activities while ensuring efficient utilization of the available resources to their optimal potentials. Resource utilization and maintenance centre on those activities that relate with maximization and keeping of educational resources at their best condition of regular completeness through supervision and control.

Resource Improvement and Supervision at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Resource improvement and supervision centre on regular upgrading and overseeing of available resources in educational institutions to serve the aim for which resources are provided, allocated, utilized and maintained at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Ogbodo (2005) expressed that improvement is an ongoing process and supervision is always necessary for such process to be on track. Resource improvement and supervision ensure that educational managers and administrators execute their duties strictly in educational institutions for improved productivity at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Resource improvement and supervision revolve around personnel development and regular upgrading of materials and improved financial resources for quality service delivery and sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. They equally centre on assisting staff and student personnel to maintain focus on various resources that can give support to improve both curriculum and extra curriculum activities in tertiary educational institutions for the achievement of sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

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Implications of Educational Resources Management for Sustainable Economic Development at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

1. Educational resources management guides the educational planners, managers and administrators in formulating policies on the provision and allocation of educational resources based on the objectives of tertiary educational institutions and general goals of education to be achieved in Nigeria.
2. Educational resources management guides the educational planners, managers and administrators in strategizing the best approach to equitably distribute the available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education based on priority needs of various units and departments in different tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.
3. Educational resources management enables the educational managers and administrators to efficiently utilize the skills, abilities competences and efforts of all individuals in tertiary educational institutions by encouraging cooperative participation of all the individuals involved in the process of mobilizing and utilizing the available scarce resources required for enhanced quality educational delivery and sustainable economic development in Nigeria.
4. Educational resources management enables the tertiary educational managers and administrators to determine priorities for actions in the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the required scarce resources available in tertiary educational institutions for improved productivity and sustainable economic development in Nigeria.
5. Educational resources management guides educational managers and administrators to minimize resources' wastage rate in preparing institutional budgets according to needs and activities of various units and departments and prepares their mind in ensuring that budgets are effectively communicated and properly complied with the daily implementation policy of tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.
6. Educational resources management leads the educational managers and administrators to strategize the most efficient means of evaluating and taking inventory of instructional facilities and materials available in educational institutions for effective instruction in tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria. It also guides them in carrying out regular supervision on staff and students activities to determine in time areas of weakness that require immediate attention at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. Educational planners, managers and administrators should always ensure that policies on the provision and allocation of educational resources are properly formulated based on the objectives of different tertiary educational institutions and general goals of education in Nigeria.
2. Educational planners, managers and administrators should always ensure that the available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria are equitably distributed based on priority needs of various units and departments of different tertiary institutions.
3. Educational managers and administrators should always ensure that priorities for actions in the allocation, utilization, maintenance and improvement of the available scarce resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria are properly determined.
4. Educational managers and administrators should employ digital means of evaluating and taking inventory of instructional facilities and materials available in educational institutions for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.
5. Educational managers and administrators should always ensure that regular supervision are carried out on staff and students' activities to determine in time areas of weakness that require immediate attention at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

Conclusion

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Educational resources management is the foundation for achieving sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria. Educational resource management creates a sense of direction in resources management actions, reduces resources wastage and enhances effective instructional delivery as well as effective academic research without much delay and conflicts. Educational resources management covers a broad scope of activities that are initiated from rational decision-making process guided by goals to be achieved. The major activities of educational resources management are resource planning and budgeting, resource provision and allocation, resource utilization and maintenance as well as resource improvement and supervision. Educational resources management must focus on adequate provision, proper allocation, efficient utilization, effective maintenance and regular improvement of the available resources required for sustainable economic development at tertiary level of education in Nigeria.

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